

Factors associated with premarital sexual behavior in adolescents at SMA X Kendari City in 2023

Farit Rezal, Fithria and Novi Hasdamayanti *

Public Health Study Program, Faculty of Public Health, Halu Oleo University, Indonesia.

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Abstract

Premarital sexual behavior is a problem and at the same time a social phenomenon that is increasingly common in society. The shift in the norms of good and bad, right and wrong, especially in the context of sexuality, is increasingly evident. Premarital sexual behavior in adolescents if not handled properly can cause cases of unwanted pregnancies (KTD) which in turn lead to abortions, STIs and HIV AIDS, and even death. The aim of this study was to determine the factors associated with premarital sexual behavior in SMA X students in Kendari City in 2022.

Method: This type of research is a quantitative study using analytical methods with a cross sectional approach. The population is all students of class X and XI with a total of 466 people who are then selected through Proportional Stratified Random Sampling with a sample of 90 people.

Result: The results showed that there was a significant relationship between knowledge (ρ value = 0,045), information sources/media (ρ value = 0,004), and peer influence (ρ value = 0,006) and premarital sex behavior. However, there is no relationship between attitude (ρ value = 0,059) and parenting style (ρ value = 0,085, with premarital sex behavior.

Conclusion: There is a relationship between knowledge of reproductive health and sexuality, sources of information/media, and peer influence with premarital sex behavior. And there is no relationship between parenting attitudes and parenting patterns with premarital sex behavior.

Keywords: Sexual Behavior; Knowledge; Attitudes; Media Information Sources; Parenting Patterns; Peer Influence

1. Background

The transition from childhood to adolescence poses risks to the health and well-being of young people. The 2018 Basic Health Research (Riskesdas) showed that reproductive health problems and risky behavior in adolescents were one of the identified problems, based on data from the 2015 Global School Health Survey, 3.3% of adolescents aged 15-19 years had AIDS, only 10% of adolescents aged 15-19 years have comprehensive knowledge about HIV AIDS and as many as 5% of adolescents have had premarital sex [1]. Premarital sexual behavior is a problem and at the same time a social phenomenon that is increasingly common in society. The shift in the norms of good and bad, right and wrong, especially in the context of sexuality, is increasingly evident. Several previous studies regarding premarital sexual behavior revealed where the first sex was carried out at a young age [2].

Indonesia, there are one million people who experience pregnancy out of wedlock, while in the world 15 million teenagers are pregnant out of wedlock every year. Indonesia is the 37th country with a high percentage of young marriages and is the second highest in ASEAN after Cambodia. Demographic and Adolescent Reproductive Health

* Corresponding author: Novi Hasdamayanti

survey results on abortion reported that 52% of adolescents had an abortion, sexually transmitted infections (STIs) were ranked in the top 10 reasons for seeking treatment in many developing countries. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that every year there are 350 million new STI sufferers in developing countries. sexual behavior in adolescents if not handled properly can cause cases of unwanted pregnancies which in turn lead to abortion, STIs and HIV AIDS, and even death [3].

According to data from the Republic of Indonesia Ministry of Health in 2015, the number of sufferers of Sexually Transmitted Diseases (STD) in adolescents was 7,335 cases, while the teenage pregnancy rate in Indonesia reached 480 out of 1,000 pregnancies, and this pregnancy in adolescents can have an impact on abortion, in In Indonesia, abortions are performed by two million women every year, and 70,000 of them are performed by unmarried young women [4].

Data from the Southeast Sulawesi National Population and Family Planning Agency, around 75% of teenagers in Kendari, both boys and girls, admit to having a girlfriend. The average age of starting courtship is 15 years. The behaviors that are often carried out by teenagers in dating are holding hands 88%, kissing lips 32% and touching/stimulating 11%. Judging from the sexual experiences of adolescents in Kendari, 7% admitted that they had had sexual intercourse. Overall, out of 14,681 teenage boys and girls who had girlfriends, 4% had had sexual intercourse [5]. Lack of knowledge, information and education about adolescent reproductive health, the dangers of premarital sex and changing partners can increase the risk of STIs, which can trigger problems that often occur around the KRR Triad, namely sexuality (premarital sex, unwanted pregnancies, abortions) to HIV/AIDS. AIDS. And based on data from the Southeast Sulawesi National Population and Family Planning Agency, several high schools in Kendari City have Youth Counseling Information Centers. High School X, Kendari City, is one of the high schools that already has an Information Center for Youth Counseling. Thus, the high school has the status of a National Priority Project, which means it is controlled or monitored directly by the center.

There are several factors that can cause premarital sexual behavior in adolescents, including parenting styles, knowledge about reproductive health, exposure to information media, peer influence and others. Based on this background, it is considered very necessary to know about the factors related to premarital sexual behavior in adolescents in one of the senior high schools in Kendari City.

2. Material and methods

This type of research is a quantitative study using analytical methods with a cross sectional approach. The population was all students of class X and XI with a total of 466 people who were then selected through Proportional Stratified Random Sampling with a sample of 90 people. Data obtained from respondents were collected, then tabulated using the SPSS program (Statistical Package For Social Science).

3. Results

3.1. Research result

Table 1 Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristics of Respondents	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Man	33	36.7
Woman	57	63.3
Age		
15	20	22.2
16	42	46.7
17	25	27.8
18	3	3.3

Source: Primary data February 2023

Data collection was obtained through direct interviews with respondents using a questionnaire. The distribution of the characteristics of the respondents can be seen in the table below:

Table 1 shows that most of the respondents were female at 63.3% and a small number of respondents were male at 36.7%. As for the age category, the highest number of respondents was at the age of 16, namely 42 respondents (46.7%), while the lowest was at the age of 18, namely 3 respondents (3.3%).

Table 2 Univariate analysis

Univariate analysis	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Premarital Sex Behavior		
Low Risk	58	64.4
High Risk	32	35.6
Knowledge Behavior		
Enough	52	57.8
Not enough	38	42.2
Attitude		
Positive Attitude	54	60.0
Negative Attitude	36	40.0
Information/media sources		
Inaccessible	41	45.6
Accessed	49	54.4
Parenting Style		
Enough	53	58.9
Not enough	37	41.1
Peer Influence		
Enough	47	52.2
Not enough	43	47.8

Source: Primary data February 2023

Table 2 shows that the majority of respondents had low-risk premarital sex, namely 58 people (64.4%), and a small number of respondents had high-risk premarital sex, namely 32 people (35.6). In the knowledge variable, a small proportion of respondents had sufficient knowledge, namely 52 people (57.8%), and the majority of respondents had insufficient knowledge, namely 38 people (42.2%). In the attitude variable, most of the respondents had a positive attitude, namely 54 people (60.0%), and a small number of respondents had a negative attitude, namely 36 people (40.0%). In the information/media source variable, most of the respondents had access to information/media sources, namely 49 people (54.4%), and a small number of respondents did not have access to information/media sources, namely 41 people (45.6%). In the parenting style variable, most of the respondents had adequate parenting, namely 53 people (58.9%), and a small number of respondents had insufficient parenting, namely 37 people (41.1%). And in the peer influence variable, most of the respondents had sufficient peer influence, namely 47 people (52.2%), and a small number of respondents had less peer influence, namely 43 people (47.8%).

Table 3 Bivariate Analysis

Variable	Premarital Sex Behavior				Amount		ρ Value
	Low Risk		High Risk		N	%	
	n	%	n	%			
Knowledge							
Enough	38	73.1	14	26.9	52	100	0,045
Not enough	20	52.6	18	47.4	38	100	
Total	58	64.4	32	35.6	90	100	
Attitude							
Positive	39	72.2	15	27.8	54	100	0,059
Negative	19	52.8	17	47.2	36	100	
Total	58	64.4	32	35.6	90	100	
Information Source (Media)							
Inaccessible	33	80.5	8	19.5	41	100	0,004
Accessed	25	51.0	24	49.0	49	100	
Total	58	64.4	32	35.6	90	100	
Parenting Style							
Enough	38	71.7	15	28.3	53	100	0,085
Not enough	20	54.1	17	45.9	37	100	
Total	58	64.4	32	35.6	90	100	
Peer Influence							
Enough	24	51.1	23	48.9	47	100	0,006
Not enough	34	79.1	9	20.9	43	100	
Total	58	64.4	32	35.6	90	100	

Source: Primary data February 2023

4. Discussion

4.1. Relation of Knowledge of Reproductive Health and Sexuality with Premarital Sex Behavior

According to Notoatmodjo (2013) knowledge is the result of knowing and this occurs after people sense a particular object. According to Amrillah, the greater the reproductive health knowledge possessed by adolescents, the lower their sexual behavior, conversely the lower the reproductive health knowledge possessed by adolescents, the greater their sexual behavior. One of the reasons for the rise of promiscuous sex among adolescents is the lack of clear and correct adolescent knowledge about sexuality [3].

The results showed that students who had sufficient knowledge of 57.8% had high-risk premarital sex behavior of 26.9% and had low-risk premarital sex behavior of 73.1%. While students who had less knowledge of 42.2% had high-risk premarital sex behavior of 47.4% and had low-risk premarital sex behavior of 52.6%. Based on the results of statistical analysis with the chi Square test, the value of $\rho = 0.045$ so ρ value $< \alpha$ (0.05) then the hypothesis H_0 is rejected so that it can be concluded that there is a relationship between knowledge and premarital sex behavior in adolescents of Senior High School X Year 2023, thus the higher the knowledge means the better sexual behavior or no premarital sex acts.

The lack of knowledge is due to the lack of information about premarital sexual education received by the respondents. This is also evidenced by the respondents who rarely get counseling about reproductive health, even though the school has a youth group, but the organization is not active. In addition, there is still a lack of implementation of premarital sex education in the family because generally talking about sex within the family is still considered taboo. As a result, adolescents without adequate knowledge about the risks of premarital sex are easily influenced by promiscuity.

The results of this study are in line with another study conducted by Yasinta (2021), with a total of 1372 respondents. It was found that 63.9% of respondents with sufficient knowledge had 12.8% of bad sexual behavior and 87.2% of good sexual behavior. While students who have less knowledge of 36.1% have bad sexual behavior by 38.7% and have good sexual behavior by 61.3%. Judging from the significant value of the research results, it shows that there is a relationship between reproductive health knowledge and sexual behavior (P value = 0.012, OR = 11.415).

Therefore, promotive and preventive efforts that can be made to prevent risky premarital sexual behavior are increasing adolescent knowledge by providing Reproductive Health Education by teaching adolescents to behave according to their gender, how to care for and maintain the cleanliness and health of their reproductive organs, providing an understanding of the consequences of each behavior. sexual harassment, how to protect oneself from sexual harassment and the consequences and disadvantages of premarital sexual acts. Reproductive Health Education does not mean opening up opportunities for free sex behavior but rather emphasizing the consequences of having sexual behavior without responsibility, including the risk of contracting sexually transmitted infections.

4.2. Relationship between Attitude and Premarital Sex Behavior

Attitudes towards premarital sexual behavior are individual views about variations in the degree to which premarital sexual behavior is permissible. According to Notoadmodjo (2012), states that attitude is a reaction or response that is still closed from a person to a stimulus or object. From the levels above, the manifestation of attitude cannot be seen with the naked eye, but can be interpreted through the stages of one's behavior [6].

The results showed that students who had a positive attitude of 60.0% had high-risk premarital sex behavior of 27.8% and had low-risk premarital sex behavior of 72.2%. Meanwhile, students who had a negative attitude of 40.0% had high-risk premarital sex behavior of 47.2% and had low-risk premarital sex behavior of 52.8%. Based on the results of statistical analysis, the value $p = 0.059$ means p value $> \alpha$ (0.05) so the hypothesis H_0 is accepted so that it can be concluded that there is no relationship between attitudes and premarital sex behavior in adolescents from high school X in 2023. This shows that some Most of the respondents have a positive attitude about premarital sex behavior.

The results of this study are in line with the results of research conducted by Muliati (2021), with a total of 89 respondents, it is known that 76 respondents obtained data that the proportion of respondents who had a positive attitude regarding premarital sex behavior was 69 people (90.8%), while for the proportion of respondents 7 people (9.2%) had a negative attitude about premarital sex behavior. This shows that the majority of respondents have a positive attitude about premarital sex behavior.

In this study, there were teenagers who thought that not having sexual intercourse before marriage helped students to avoid the risk of unwanted pregnancies. Even though most of the respondents had a positive attitude or avoided premarital sex, there were still some teenagers who thought that having sex with a boyfriend or partner was considered a sign of love for a partner.

Most of the respondents thought that Premarital Sexual Education was not that important to know and they thought that Premarital Sexual Education should only be given to adults because for them Premarital Sexual Education and reproductive health are still taboo. Sex, which is still considered taboo, results in a lack of knowledge and low perception and self-control in adolescents, causing a sense of irresponsibility with their sexual rights. The importance of sexual education for adolescents aims to guide and provide explanations regarding changes in the function of the sexual organs which are stages that must be experienced in life as well as understanding the value of sexuality.

Therefore, adolescents are encouraged to practice sexual abstinence by abstaining from engaging in risky sexual behavior and having the courage to refuse when someone invites them to do so. Teenagers also need to comply with religious teachings and norms that apply in society in order to avoid risky sexual behavior.

4.3. Relationship between Information Sources/Media and Premarital Sexual Behavior

Media is one of the external factors that has a close relationship with sexual behavior in adolescents. When adolescents live in an environment that provides more opportunities to learn with technology, they use it to meet their needs and desires, including in terms of socio-sexual development [7].

The results showed that 45.6% of students who did not have access to information sources/media had high-risk premarital sex behavior of 19.5% and had low-risk premarital sex behavior of 80.5%. Meanwhile, 54.4% of students who accessed had high-risk premarital sex behavior of 49.0% and had low-risk premarital sex behavior of 51.0%. Based on the results of statistical analysis, the value of $\rho = 0.004$ is ρ value $< \alpha$ (0, 05) so the H_0 hypothesis is rejected so that it can be concluded that there is a relationship between sources of information media and premarital sex behavior in high school adolescents X Year 2023. The results of this study indicate that more than half of the respondents have received information about premarital sexual behavior (pornography). From several existing sources, the internet with the highest number of accesses was 43.3% and the least was magazines, namely 2.2%. This is because technological advances are increasingly rapidly making it easier for anyone to connect to the internet. The sexual drive which is the basic need of every individual coupled with the development of growth hormone in adolescence and high curiosity increases adolescent interest in pornography, adolescents then find out through the easiest and safest media that can be accessed, namely the internet.

The results of this study are in line with the results of research conducted by Harni (2016), with a total of 90 respondents, it is known that students who accessed were 92.2%, had risky sexual behavior by 79.5% and had non-risk sexual behavior by 20.5%. While students who were not accessed by 7.8% had risky sexual behavior by 14.3% and had non-risk sexual behavior by 85.7%. The results of the Fisher's Exact Test statistical analysis obtained a P value or a significance value of 0.010 and α was 0.05. the P value is smaller than α , then the hypothesis H_0 is rejected, meaning that there is a relationship between access to media information and sexual behavior.

The rise of misinformation about sex that is spread both in electronic media and in the media has an impact on a person's behavior. The high promiscuity is influenced by the sophistication of the internet, which broadcasts many porn sites. Adolescents who have never fully understood sexuality will try and imitate what they see.

Therefore, prevention efforts that can be done is to use good information by teenagers. This can happen because with the use of good information sources, adolescents will increase knowledge about reproductive health which will have an impact on adolescent attitudes which in turn can affect premarital sexual behavior in adolescents. In addition, the government also plays an important role in this matter where it is necessary to emphasize the laws governing pornographic media.

4.4. Parenting Parenting Relationship with Premarital Sex Behavior

Various interactions between adolescents and their parents delay and even reduce sexual behavior in adolescents. Adolescents who are supervised by their parents, adolescents with authoritarian parenting, adolescents who come from conservative families and hold strong traditions and adolescents who have intimate relationships with their parents will delay the age of first having sexual intercourse [8].

The results showed that 58.9% of respondents who had sufficient parenting style had high-risk premarital sex behavior of 28.3% and had low-risk premarital sex behavior of 71.7%. Meanwhile, respondents who had less parenting style 41.1% had high-risk premarital sex behavior of 45.9% and had low-risk premarital sex behavior of 54.1%. Based on the results of statistical analysis, the value of $\rho = 0.085$ means ρ value $> \alpha$ (0.05) so the H_0 hypothesis is accepted so that it can be concluded that there is no relationship between parenting parents and premarital sex behavior in high school adolescents X Year 2023.

The results also showed that 28.3% of the respondents had quite good parenting but had high-risk premarital sexual behavior, this is because parents who care for their children always direct their children's behavior without being given the freedom to express opinions or feelings to other people. besides that, parents also care for their children by exercising control and giving strict rules, so that children feel pressured and look for outlets elsewhere by doing negative things. The results of this study are in line with the results of research conducted by Rambani (2018), with a total of 166 respondents, it is known that respondents who received sufficient parenting from their parents were more likely to engage in sexual behavior (18.1%) than those who did not engage in sexual behavior (5.4%), while respondents who had parenting style were more or less likely to engage in sexual behavior (60.2%) compared to those who did not engage in sexual behavior (16.3%). From the chi square test, the value of $p = 0.810$ ($p > 0.05$) was obtained, which means that there is no significant relationship between parenting styles and sexual behavior.

The researcher's assumption that parenting factors are not related to the formation of premarital sexual behavior is due to other factors that influence the respondents to have premarital sexual behavior. In this study, respondents who received sufficient or insufficient parenting styles both showed high-risk sexual behavior incidents compared to respondents who had low-risk sexual behavior. The biggest urge to have premarital sex comes from yourself.

Therefore, one of the efforts that can be made in dealing with premarital sex behavior problems in adolescents is by providing premarital sex education. In this case, premarital sex education should ideally be given first by parents at home. Good premarital sex education will help adolescents to know the risks of their sexual attitudes and teach adult sexual decision-making, so as not to cause harm to themselves or their parents.

4.5. The Relationship between Peer Influence and Premarital Sex Behavior

Risky premarital sexual behavior in adolescents can also be influenced by peers. The interactions that are made between friends, the pressure that is given makes teenagers follow the behavior of their group mates. The existence of social pressure in interacting with friends is one of the factors in inviting sexual behavior [9]

The results showed that respondents with peer influence in the moderate category of 52.2% had high-risk premarital sex behavior of 48.9% and had low-risk premarital sex behavior of 51.1%. Meanwhile, respondents with peer influence in the less category of 47.8% had high-risk premarital sex behavior of 20.9% and had low-risk premarital sex behavior of 79.1%. Based on the results of statistical analysis, the value of $\rho = 0.006$ is ρ value $< \alpha$ (0.05) so the H_0 hypothesis is rejected so that it can be concluded that there is a relationship between peer influence and premarital sex behavior in adolescents of Senior High School X Kendari City in 2023.

The results of this study are in line with the results of research conducted by Irma (2022), with a total of 174 respondents, it is known that respondents with considerable peer influence engage in high-risk sexual behavior (66.67%) compared to those who engage in low-risk sexual behavior (6.94%), while respondents with less peer influence had high-risk sexual behavior (33.3%) compared to those with low-risk sexual behavior (93.6%). The value of $p = 0.000$ ($p < 0.05$) was obtained, which means that there is a significant relationship between peer influence and premarital sex behavior.

This shows that peers are quite influential with premarital sexual behavior, which means that the higher the influence of peers, the greater the risk of premarital sexual behavior occurring. The peer influence factor is related to premarital sexual behavior, in adolescents it can occur because of the emotional connection and intimacy between adolescents, it is undeniable that they invite each other in all ways, including trying something new, such as premarital sex.

In addition, there were also 87.8% of respondents in this study who obtained a lot of information about adolescent sexuality from their peers, this happened because peers were more open in providing information about sex than their parents or family. Information obtained from parents is often unsatisfactory because in general it contains more moral messages, while sexual and reproductive health information is not conveyed in its entirety because it is considered a taboo subject to discuss. Peer influence is one of the factors in the occurrence of premarital sex in adolescents. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out routine group counseling, information and education activities for adolescents and peers regarding risky sexual behavior in adolescents. In addition, premarital sexual behavior can be overcome by being able to filter out influences from their environment, so as not to imitate the negative things that are done by those around them, by further strengthening their faith or religiosity.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results of research and discussion of the relationship between knowledge, attitudes, sources of information/media, parenting styles, and peer influence. Then it can be concluded as follows:

- There is a relationship between knowledge about reproductive health and sexuality with premarital sex behavior in adolescents of Senior High School X Kendari City in 2023
- 2. There is no relationship between attitude and premarital sex behavior in adolescents of Senior High School X Kendari City in 2023
- There is a relationship between sources of information/media with premarital sex behavior in adolescents of Senior High School X Kendari City in 2023
- There is no relationship between parenting style and premarital sexual behavior in adolescents of Senior High School X Kendari City in 2023

- There is a relationship between peer influence and premarital sex behavior in adolescents of Senior High School X Kendari City in 2023

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

All authors in the making of this scientific article have no conflict of interest.

Statement of ethical approval

The present study did not require an evaluation by an ethics committee, since as it is a systematic review, it uses secondary data sources.

Statement of informed consent

All informants/respondents involved in this study have stated their consent as informants/respondents to be interviewed and provided information/information in accordance with research needs.

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